

IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON THE ECONOMY AND LABOR MARKET

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Annotation The article analyzes from a scientific point of view the impact of migration on the economy and the labor market, the policy of meeting the demand for low-skilled labor, the issues of changing the mechanism for migrants to enter the labor market.

Key words: migration, migrant, economy, market, labor, qualification, worker.

Economically motivated migration is not random: workers move from labor markets where demand and wages are low to where demand and wages are higher. At a time when the level of education in the countries of the world began to rise, and the population began to age, the demand for low-skilled workers exceeded supply. To meet this excess demand, young, less educated immigrants from relatively poor countries on the OECD periphery began to arrive. In addition to meeting excess demand in labor markets, migration policy is designed to solve other problems. In many cases, social and political objectives require restrictions on the influx of migrants and conflict with the needs of the labor market, leading to market distortions and cultural, political and social problems¹. Available evidence and comparisons of different experiences suggest that implementing policies that can resist market forces is next to impossible. Instead, governments should design policies in response to market forces. One example of such a policy is temporary migration schemes.

¹ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich, Mehmanov Zikrillo Mirzokhidovich, and Sobirov Ogabek Navro'zbekovich. The Role of the Category of Chance in the Analysis of Social Life. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. Volume 2 Issue 2, (2023), 246-249.

Consider possible ways to overcome such resistance. The free movement of labor across borders brings not only losses to certain categories of existing workers, but also benefits in terms of increasing overall efficiency². Governments face the difficult task of developing policies to provide funding and compensation for the loss of affected workers in order to dampen political resistance to migration. In recent decades, many eminent economists have proposed market mechanisms to solve two problems: identifying who should be allowed to immigrate and work in a given country, and determining ways to extract some economic benefit to compensate workers who suffer losses. G. Becker suggested that the US government sell visas to foreigners instead of setting quotas. Foreign workers (or employers), with the potential to earn the most in terms of income, can bid the highest bid for visas, and in this way the government treasury will receive income that would otherwise be received by migrants and their employers. The sale of visas has also been proposed as a means of reducing human trafficking or compensating local workers who have lost out to migrants. In recent years, various citizenship/passport-for-investment programs have emerged. These proposals do not exclude the inefficiency of the relevant market mechanism. Despite the excess demand for work permits, there is no supply side in the labor market in this mechanism. An immigrant needs a work permit for formal employment under a contract of employment, the government technically sells such a permit to an immigrant³. However, the real owners of this permit are citizens who have the implied right to accept the right to work granted to them. The mechanism proposed in the work of M. Lokshin provides for the provision of compensation to people who are ready to "sell" this right for a certain period. In the proposal of these researchers, citizens of working age are allowed to "rent out" to foreign workers

² Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich, Ergashev Zakhridin Muradkabilovich, and Saidov Abukarim Abdurahimovich. The Influence of the Transport and Communication System on Social Relations. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. Volume 2 Issue 2, (2023), 209-212.

³ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich, Ergashev Zakhridin Muradkabilovich, and Saidov Abukarim Abdurahimovich. The Influence of the Transport and Communication System on Social Relations. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. Volume 2 Issue 2, (2023), 209-212.

their right to accept a job offer. The government could set up an Internet platform that would establish contacts between citizens who wish to auction their right to accept a job offer and foreigners who need a work permit. When a citizen decides to "lease" his right to accept a job offer, this right is transferred to the foreigner on a temporary basis in the form of a work permit, and money is transferred to the person who waived his right. Such a mechanism allows citizens who are likely to suffer economic losses from migration to receive direct compensation for their losses. By purchasing a work permit, a migrant worker is entitled to accept any job offer in the country. At the end of the contract, the work permit is returned to the original owner. The creation of an anonymous and transparent market for work permits can reduce political resistance to migration by helping to internalize the externalities generated (or perceived) by migrants in the host country. The recipient country reaps a number of benefits from the introduction of such a policy, as low-paid workers with low labor productivity will be replaced by migrants with higher productivity, which will contribute to GDP growth and increase tax revenues. Replacement workers receive direct compensation, which reduces the need for complex and inefficient social assistance programs for them⁴. The scheme may involve maintaining the total number of jobs in the recipient country at a certain level in order to prevent a situation where migration leads to unemployment. The work permit market can be seen not only as an effective immigration management tool, but also as a social safety net. Such an approach is likely to promote freer international migration.

One possible way to attract funds from those who benefit from migration to finance the costs of labor movement is to change the mechanisms by which migrants enter the labor market in the recipient country by moving from quantitative restrictions to price mechanisms. Currently, almost all receiving countries use quotas to regulate the flow of legal and registered immigrants. Governments decide on the number of immigrants with certain levels of education,

⁴ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. -P.406-410.

with certain professions and belonging to certain sectors, who will be allowed to work in their countries. The use of quotas creates several problems. First, officials, not employers or labor market representatives, estimate the number of immigrants who will be allowed to enter the country. It is quite difficult to determine which type of migration will be most beneficial to the host country, especially in the long term. In addition, labor market needs can change rapidly over time. Second, quota-based systems are subject to risks of rent-seeking behavior and corruption, as businesses may seek to persuade government officials to issue quota-based permits in favor of their industries. Thirdly, the quotas set are too low and the incentives for illegal entry are high, resulting in a large number of undocumented migrants in the country. They work in the informal labor market, are not eligible for social protection, and generate negative externalities that affect the lowest-skilled workers that the state has tried to protect. Fourth, quotas do not generate revenue for the state treasury. On the contrary, they are beneficial only to those enterprises that are lucky enough to hire an immigrant (who received a visa with the right to work for hire). Intermediary firms that provide services for the selection of migrants, and those that engage in human trafficking and help undocumented migrants, charge a considerable fee for their services. There are several ways to replace quota regimes with tax regimes to regulate the influx of immigrants, including through the introduction of an additional tax on income, fees for issuing visas, and a system of auctions for the sale of visas. Some countries, such as Malaysia and Singapore, levy fees on immigrants. The levying of taxes, fees and charges instead of quotas has many clear advantages, although none of these measures have yet been adequately assessed. Mechanisms like these would provide government with revenue to support workers who experience economic hardship as a result of migration, especially older, relatively low-skilled people who are less able to change jobs or move to other industries⁵. Employers will also be able to

⁵ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich, Mehmanov Zikrillo Mirzokhidovich, and Sobirov Ogabek Navro'zbekovich. The Role of the Category of Chance in the Analysis of Social Life. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education. Volume 2 Issue 2, (2023), 246-249.

respond more quickly to fluctuations in the economic environment and, if necessary, hire additional workers. Under a quota regime, enterprises are not able to rapidly expand production, even if they are willing to pay for the issuance of work permits. Governments will also be able to adjust fees/taxes more quickly to respond to changes in the labor market. Fee-based regimes are also likely to reduce cultural hostility towards immigrants, as they provide the necessary "tax" revenues and can no longer be blamed for living in a country "for free". In world trade, the replacement of the quota regime by tariffs took many decades. It will take the same amount of time to introduce and enforce such an immigration policy, but it is worth trying.

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